

Optimized meta-scheduling in Galaxy using TPV Broker

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Abstract. Effective resource scheduling is critical in high-performance (HPC) and high-throughput computing (HTC) environments, where traditional scheduling systems struggle with resource contention, data locality, and fault tolerance. Meta-scheduling, which abstracts multiple schedulers for unified job allocation, addresses these challenges.

Galaxy, a widely used platform for data-intensive computational analysis, employs the *Total Perspective Vortex (TPV)* system for resource scheduling. With over 550,000 users, Galaxy aims to optimize scheduling efficiency in large-scale environments. While TPV offers flexibility, its decision-making can be enhanced by incorporating real-time resource availability and job status.

This paper introduces the TPV Broker, a meta-scheduling framework that integrates real-time resource data to enable dynamic, data-aware scheduling. TPV Broker enhances scalability, resource utilization, and scheduling efficiency in Galaxy, offering potential for further improvements in distributed computing environments.

1 Introduction

Rapid growth in computational demand across various scientific, industrial, and commercial sectors has resulted in the widespread deployment of large-scale distributed computing systems. These systems, often composed of clusters, grids, and cloud infrastructures, provide vast computational resources for handling data-intensive workloads. However, managing and allocating these resources remains a significant challenge, particularly when scheduling jobs across such heterogeneous environments. Inefficient resource scheduling can lead to prolonged

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execution times, suboptimal resource utilization, and energy wastage. These issues are particularly pronounced in HPC and domains, where workloads are diverse and computational resources are distributed across various infrastructures [1,2].

A promising solution to these challenges is *meta-scheduling*, which facilitates job execution coordination across independent systems. By abstracting the underlying complexities of individual schedulers, a meta-scheduler can enable dynamic job allocation across multiple infrastructures, optimizing resource utilization and reducing execution time. Meta-scheduling approaches allow systems to adapt to varying workloads and resource availability, ultimately improving system efficiency [3,4]. These capabilities are critical in large-scale platforms such as Galaxy [5], an open-source, domain-agnostic framework widely used for computational data analysis and workflow development. Galaxy processes millions of jobs (units of execution that run specific tools on given input data) for a global user base of over 550,000 researchers, utilizing local HPC clusters, cloud environments, and remote computing infrastructures such as Pulsar, a system that enables job execution on remote resources without requiring a shared filesystem [6]. Managing such a large and diverse workload necessitates intelligent scheduling mechanisms that dynamically allocate resources based on job characteristics and real-time resource availability [7].

In the context of the Galaxy project, TPV has been developed as a robust meta-scheduling tool for efficient job routing, seamlessly integrating with Galaxy’s diverse architecture, which includes heterogeneous resources, user-added compute and storage, varied job types, and training infrastructures (Figure. 1). TPV allows for the definition of scheduling policies using a flexible YAML-based framework, enabling precise control over job execution parameters such as CPU, memory, and GPU allocation [8]. However, while TPV provides effective job scheduling within the Galaxy environment, it faces limitations in real-time resource awareness, queue status tracking, and data locality considerations. This can lead to suboptimal decisions when resources are allocated without fully understanding system load, geographical location, or data proximity.

To address these limitations, we introduce the *TPV Broker*, a novel intelligent matchmaking system that enhances TPV’s scheduling decisions. The TPV Broker integrates real-time system metrics, such as resource availability, queue lengths, and job execution history, using a fuzzy matchmaking algorithm to provide more informed scheduling choices. Additionally, it incorporates geographical proximity of both compute and storage environments to minimize data movement and reduce energy consumption. By dynamically ranking available compute resources based on factors like CPU, memory, and GPU availability, as well as data locality, the TPV Broker optimizes resource allocation and job execution efficiency. This system enhances the scheduling process and contributes to the goal of green computing by improving energy utilization [9,10].

Through the introduction of the TPV Broker, Galaxy’s meta-scheduling capabilities are significantly improved, leading to more efficient job execution, reduced operational costs, and an overall more sustainable computational envi-

Fig. 1. Galaxy’s architecture supports thousands of tools, a large and diverse user base, varied computing environments (both local and remote), user-provided compute and storage (Bring Your Own Compute (BYOC) and Bring Your Own Storage (BYOS)), heterogeneous resources, diverse job types, and dedicated training infrastructures.

ronment. This paper discusses the architecture and functionality of the TPV Broker, demonstrating its potential to redefine job scheduling in large-scale distributed systems by integrating real-time metrics and intelligent matchmaking techniques.

2 Related Work

Job scheduling and resource management in large-scale distributed systems have been widely studied, with centralized and decentralized approaches being the most prominent. Centralized meta-scheduling systems, such as DIRAC [11], GridWay [12], and Pilot-Data [9], offer simplicity and global policy enforcement but struggle with scalability, fault tolerance, and data locality, often becoming bottlenecks as the system grows [13,14]. Decentralized systems like RADICAL-Pilot [15] and the Globus Toolkit [16] address scalability and fault tolerance by distributing scheduling responsibilities across multiple schedulers, but they introduce complexities such as communication overhead and resource conflicts [17,18].

Hybrid approaches, such as Kubernetes [10] and REEF [19], combine centralized orchestration with decentralized resource management to balance simplicity and scalability, but they tend to be more complex to implement and manage.

The approach presented in this paper enhances centralized scheduling through the *TPV Broker*, which coordinates job routing and resource allocation across

multiple Galaxy’s. While each Galaxy server can independently submit jobs to computational endpoints (also referred to as compute destinations or remote endpoints are used interchangeably in this text), the TPV Broker improves scheduling efficiency by providing real-time insights into resource availability, optimizing decisions, and reducing bottlenecks. This hybrid solution combines the benefits of centralized coordination with the flexibility of decentralized job submission, ensuring scalability, efficiency, and adaptability in large-scale systems.

3 Galaxy and computational workload management

Galaxy provides robust computational workload management, enabling efficient job scheduling and resource allocation across distributed environments. This is achieved through a combination of *TPV*, *job runners* and *Pulsar*, which facilitate job execution and resource management.

3.1 Job runners and Pulsar

The *job runners* in Galaxy are responsible for handling job execution within various computational environments, such as local clusters, (remote-) cloud infrastructures, and HPC systems. These job runners interact with Galaxy’s meta-scheduler, TPV, to submit jobs to computational environments with available resources. Galaxy supports a diverse range of job runners, including the *LocalJobRunner* for local executions and the *GridEngineJobRunner* for grid and cluster systems such as HTCondor, SLURM, and PBS [20]. Additionally, Galaxy is compatible with any DRMAA-compliant scheduler, which allows it to interact with job scheduling systems for job submission, control, and monitoring, and supports containerized execution environments like Docker and Kubernetes, enabling seamless integration with a wide variety of computing infrastructures.

By default, Galaxy requires a shared filesystem between the application server and the job execution environment, which can limit the flexibility and scalability of the system. Pulsar addresses this limitation by enabling remote job execution without needing a shared filesystem. Pulsar is a Python-based server application running on a remote compute resource that can interface with any of the Distributed Resource Managers (DRMs) supported by Galaxy, including those previously mentioned, Kubernetes clusters, Windows machines, and others. Pulsar accepts jobs from a Galaxy server (via a *PulsarJobRunner*), submits them to the local compute resource, and sends the results back to the originating Galaxy server.

Pulsar provides a flexible architecture by acting as a middleware that connects Galaxy with remote clusters or schedulers. It facilitates the seamless integration of Galaxy with external computing environments, ensuring that Galaxy can interact with a wide range of job execution systems. While Pulsar is not responsible for scheduling decisions, it is critical to ensure that jobs are executed using the appropriate resources and correctly handled with the necessary input and output data. Pulsar can be deployed in various environments, including

cloud or on-premises infrastructures, making it a versatile tool for integrating remote compute resources with the Galaxy platform.

3.2 Job scheduling in Galaxy

The *Total Perspective Vortex (TPV)* is a Python-based plugin that enables advanced meta-scheduling in Galaxy by providing flexible job routing to the appropriate DRMs. TPV provides fine-grained control over job execution by specifying resource allocations, such as CPU, memory, and GPU, through a YAML-based configuration file. This enables flexible scheduling policies that allocate jobs based on their precise resource requirements (Figure. 1).

Within the TPV framework, jobs are assigned to computational resources through a tagging system defined in the YAML configuration. A destination refers to a specific computational resource or group of resources, that can execute jobs. Each destination is associated with scheduling tags defining its capabilities and includes the maximum available computational resources such as memory size, core count, or GPU availability. These tags allow jobs to be routed to the most appropriate destination based on their resource requirements. The routing decisions are governed by rules that prioritize or avoid certain destinations, depending on the job's resource needs. However, these default rules are limited, as TPV does not consider factors like real-time system load, data proximity, or locality. The system can be extended with custom Python-based code to enhance the scheduling process, enabling more sophisticated decision-making and dynamic routing. This flexibility allows TPV to address the complex and changing resource management needs.

4 Meta-scheduling with TPV Broker

The TPV Broker is an extension of TPV designed to enhance meta-scheduling by incorporating real-time system metrics, such as resource availability, queue lengths, and job execution history. It consists of several interconnected components: a central meta-scheduling Python application that interfaces with TPV via an API; an InfluxDB, a time-series database that collects and allows querying of metrics from all compute destinations; a Python-based RabbitMQ (a system that routes messages between components) producer-consumer system; and, finally, the Galaxy Job Radar, which provides a visualization of the job flow across the system.

Figure. 2 presents the architecture of the TPV Broker. In this system, user-submitted jobs are routed through Galaxy, which interfaces with the TPV plugin to transfer job-related data. TPV then communicates with the TPV Broker via a REST API, enabling the Broker to retrieve real-time resource utilization and performance metrics from InfluxDB. The Broker evaluates key factors such as data locality and the availability of heterogeneous compute resources. Leveraging these parameters, the Broker applies a fuzzy matchmaking algorithm to determine the most appropriate destination for job execution, ensuring optimal resource allocation across the compute infrastructure.

Fig. 2. TPV Broker architecture.

4.1 Producer-consumer model for real-time resource tracking in meta-scheduling

Efficient meta-scheduling in large-scale distributed environments requires continuous resource availability monitoring across diverse compute destinations. To achieve this, we have developed a producer-consumer model [21] that dynamically collects and updates real-time system metrics, ensuring scheduling decisions are based on the most up-to-date resource states. This model enables Galaxy’s TPV Broker to make informed scheduling choices by integrating real-time insights into system load, queue lengths, and available computing resources.

In this model, each compute destination (HPC/cloud/Pulsar endpoint) runs a producer component that is executed periodically. This producer interacts with the local job scheduler (e.g., HTCondor) to retrieve key system metrics, including available CPU cores, memory usage, GPU availability, and average system load. These collected metrics are then published as messages into a RabbitMQ queue, effectively creating a lightweight, decentralized system that continuously reports resource availability to the central scheduling system.

A corresponding consumer component is run using Telegraf at regular intervals, retrieving these messages from RabbitMQ and updating a centralized time series database (InfluxDB) with the latest metrics. This ensures that the TPV Broker always has an accurate view of the current state of each compute destination. Additionally, destinations are marked offline if they fail to report within a predefined time threshold or if their last reported message is outdated. This automated status management prevents jobs from being dispatched to unresponsive or overloaded endpoints, improving system reliability and efficiency.

Galaxy achieves a more adaptive and data-driven meta-scheduling strategy by integrating these real-time system metrics. The model optimizes workload

distribution and supports green computing initiatives by directing jobs to underutilized or energy-efficient resources. This dynamic feedback mechanism ensures that TPV scheduling remains responsive to evolving system conditions, significantly enhancing job execution efficiency across heterogeneous computing infrastructures.

4.2 Fuzzy matchmaking for dynamic meta-scheduling

At the core of this approach is the Python application [22] where we implement a *fuzzy matchmaking algorithm* described in the DAIS2014 paper [23,24]. The fuzzy logic-based algorithm employed ensures that job allocation decisions are made by evaluating multiple criteria, such as available CPU slots, memory size, and other relevant system characteristics, which it retrieves from the InfluxDB. The fuzzy matchmaking approach is based on the *Takagi-Sugeno fuzzy model* [25,26], which is effective for dealing with uncertain or imprecise information often present in distributed environments like those encountered in computational grids.

When a job is submitted to Galaxy, it comes with specific resource requirements, such as CPU, memory, and GPU. TPV first performs an initial matching by evaluating these requirements against the statically defined resources of available compute destinations. The TPV Broker then refines this selection by dynamically assessing real-time resource availability reported by different Pulsar endpoints, ensuring that jobs are allocated to the most suitable and currently available resources. The fuzzy matchmaking process evaluates the degree of match between the job's resource needs and the available resources on the computational endpoints. The fuzzy matchmaking approach operates as follows:

- **Fuzzification of input data:** The first step in fuzzy matchmaking is *fuzzification*, where both the job requirements and the available resources are converted into fuzzy sets. For example, the required CPU slots and memory size are translated into fuzzy categories such as 'low', 'medium' and 'high' according to predefined thresholds. The available resources reported by the Pulsar endpoints are also converted into fuzzy sets to represent their degree of availability, such as "sufficient," "moderate," or "insufficient."
- **Rule-based decision making:** The fuzzy matchmaker then applies a set of rules to determine the most appropriate match between job requirements and available resources. These rules are formulated based on the fuzzified inputs, for example:

IF CPU-Slots-Size(job) IS Allocatable-In-CPUslots(resource)
AND Memory-Image(job) IS Allocatable-In-VirtualMemory(resource)

The fuzzy logic algorithm uses *AND operators* to combine the conditions of multiple input attributes, with the result being a fuzzy value representing the suitability of each resource for the job.

- **Aggregation and defuzzification:** Once the rules are applied, the fuzzy outputs corresponding to different resources are aggregated. The aggregation process involves combining the fuzzy results from different domains and ranking them according to their membership values. The final step is *defuzzification*, which translates the fuzzy set back into a crisp value representing the best match. In this case, the fuzzy set for each potential resource is defuzzified to produce a single output, indicating the resource/endpoint/destination with the highest degree of suitability for the job.
- **Scheduling decision:** Based on the defuzzified output, the TPV Broker selects the most suitable resource from the list of available Pulsar endpoints. If multiple resources are deemed suitable, the one with the highest match score is selected. The fuzzy approach ensures that the scheduler is not limited to exact matches but can also account for varying degrees of compatibility between job requirements and resource availability, leading to more flexible and adaptive job scheduling.
- **Real-time feedback and dynamic adjustment:** An important feature of this scheduling approach is its ability to continuously receive real-time feedback from the Pulsar endpoints, allowing it to dynamically adapt scheduling based on changes in resource availability, job queue status, and system load. As a result, the fuzzy matchmaking algorithm can continuously refine its scheduling decisions to optimize resource utilization, considering fluctuations in system conditions.

Algorithm implementation The algorithm described below explains how jobs are distributed to compute endpoints, considering job requirements (CPU and memory) and resource availability at each endpoint. This algorithm is executed on the TPV Broker, which collects histograms of available resources (CPUs and memory) from each endpoint. Based on this data, the TPV Broker matches the job’s resource needs with the available resources at each endpoint. For further details, refer to Algorithm 1.

Algorithm explanation

- **Step 1: Initialize the job requirements and endpoints**
The job requirements (CPU and memory) are defined, and the available compute endpoints are initialized. The histograms of available CPUs and memory across the machines in each endpoint are collected to represent the distribution of resources in the system.
- **Step 2: Filter out endpoints that cannot meet basic resource requirements**
We filter out endpoints that cannot meet the basic job requirements. Specifically, any endpoint that does not have enough free CPUs or memory (based on its resource histograms) is excluded from the list of viable endpoints. Only those endpoints with machines having sufficient resources are considered for allocation.

- **Step 3: Calculate the distance to the input data location**
For each viable endpoint, the algorithm calculates the distance between the job’s input data location and the compute endpoint. This distance helps to prioritize endpoints that are physically closer to the data, reducing data transfer time and improving overall efficiency.
- **Step 4: Calculate the matching score for each endpoint**
For each viable endpoint, the algorithm computes a matching score that reflects how well the endpoint matches the job’s requirements. This is done using two matching factors:
 - **Queue matching factor (qm)**: Based on the median queue time and the number of jobs in the queue at the endpoint.
 - **Compute matching factor (cm)**: Based on the median run time and the number of running jobs at the endpoint.
 These factors are combined to calculate the endpoint’s final matching score.
- **Step 5: Sort endpoints by matching score and distance to data location**
After calculating the matching scores, the viable endpoints are sorted. First, the endpoints are sorted by their matching score in descending order to prioritize the best-fitting resources. If multiple endpoints have the same matching score, they are further sorted based on their proximity to the data location, with closer endpoints being preferred.
- **Step 6: Allocate jobs to sorted endpoints**
The jobs are allocated to the endpoints based on the sorted list. The job allocation process follows the order of the sorted list, ensuring that jobs are assigned to the most suitable endpoints in terms of both resource availability and proximity to the data.
- **Step 7: Return the allocated endpoints**
Finally, the algorithm returns the list of allocated endpoints, ordered by their suitability to execute the job. The returned list indicates which compute destinations have been chosen for the execution of each job.

4.3 Advantages and limitations

The meta-scheduling approach of the TPV broker offers several significant advantages over basic scheduling with TPV:

- **Improved load balancing**: The job load can be balanced across resources by allocating jobs to the most suitable resources based on a set of flexible criteria, which helps prevent resource underutilization or overloading.
- **Data-aware scheduling**: By considering job data requirements alongside resource availability, we minimize data transfer overhead, ensuring that computation and data storage are co-located when possible.
- **Adaptability to dynamic environments**: The real-time information provided by the Pulsar endpoints enables the Broker to respond to changing conditions, such as fluctuating resource availability and varying job demands. This adaptability ensures efficient resource utilization even in highly dynamic environments.

However, while this approach offers numerous benefits, it also faces limitations when scaled to handle larger systems with increased jobs, users, and computational resources. Although central to the scheduling process, the TPV Broker may become a bottleneck as the system grows, limiting the overall throughput of job submissions. Challenges and limitations include:

- **Bottlenecks in scheduling:** As the TPV Broker must process large volumes of resource data and job requests in real-time this could overwhelm the system.
- **Dependency on central coordination:** While TPVs can operate independently, the TPV Broker optimizes scheduling decisions across distributed resources. If unavailable, job execution continues, but resource allocation may become less efficient, potentially leading to longer queue times or suboptimal utilization.

4.4 Job flow and resource utilization monitoring

To enhance the observability of job execution across distributed remote computing environments (the set of Pulsar endpoints), we developed *Galaxy Job Radar* (Figure. 3). This real-time visualization tool provides insights into job flow and resource utilization within the Galaxy’s meta-scheduling framework. Galaxy Job Radar serves a dual purpose: first, as a promotional tool, it offers an interactive and visually engaging representation of Galaxy servers and their associated pulsar endpoints through dynamic maps and color-coded job flow graphs; and second, as a monitoring tool for administrators, enabling both real-time tracking of global job distribution patterns, as well as insight into its history, it provides means of early detection of potential infrastructure issues.

A prototype implementation of Galaxy Job Radar is available online [27], and its source code is publicly accessible [28]. The tool visualizes the job flow from Galaxy servers to Pulsars, leveraging data stored in the InfluxDB database. Further, Galaxy Job Radar maintains an internal database for historical data storage, allowing for history playback and retrospective analyses of job execution and distribution patterns. Currently, the tool retrieves real-time metrics on the number of queued and running jobs for each Pulsar. Ongoing development efforts aim to incorporate additional metrics such as the historical job failure rates, frequently used tools, and anonymized user statistics per Pulsar endpoint, among various others. Future enhancements will include retrospective analyses of scheduling efficiency, enabling deeper insights into how well jobs were distributed based on key performance metrics. Galaxy Job Radar enables improved resource management, anomaly detection, and strategic optimizations for large-scale scientific computing workloads by providing a centralized visualization of job flow across a distributed infrastructure.

Fig. 3. Galaxy Job Radar visualization.

5 Conclusions and future work

This paper presents a novel meta-scheduling framework for Galaxy, leveraging the Total Perspective Vortex (TPV) meta-scheduler and the TPV Broker to optimize job scheduling in distributed computing environments. TPV offers a flexible, rule-based scheduling mechanism, while the TPV Broker extends its capabilities by incorporating real-time resource tracking, dynamic ranking algorithms, and optimizations for data locality. These components collectively aim to enhance scheduling efficiency, reduce data movement, and support energy-efficient computing in large-scale systems.

We introduced a producer-consumer model for real-time resource tracking. Using RabbitMQ as a message broker, the system efficiently collects resource metrics—including queue lengths, system loads, available resources, and job execution patterns—enabling the TPV to make adaptive, informed scheduling decisions. Additionally, the Galaxy Job Radar visualization tool provides valuable insights into job flow across Pulsar endpoints, improving system monitoring and enhancing administrative decision-making.

While the primary focus of this paper is on the design and functionality of the TPV Broker, future work will involve a detailed evaluation of the system’s performance under various computational workloads. This will include refining the fuzzy-logic-based scheduling algorithm to better adapt to dynamic workload patterns and integrating machine learning techniques for predictive scheduling and workload characterization. Expanding the capabilities of Galaxy Job Radar to incorporate historical performance analysis and job efficiency metrics will provide insights into the scheduling process. Moreover, large-scale evaluations

in real-world deployments will ensure the robustness and scalability of the system across heterogeneous computational environments, validating its practical applicability in diverse settings.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank the EuroScienceGateway consortium for their continuous support and collaboration in developing this work. We also extend our gratitude to the Galaxy Australia team for implementing the Total Perspective Vortex and to the broader Galaxy Project and its community for their ongoing support and innovation.

Funding

This work was supported by the *EuroScienceGateway* project, which is part of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) initiative. The project is funded by the *European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme* under grant agreement No. 101057388.

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Algorithm 1 TPV Broker meta-scheduling for job allocation

- 1: **Input:** Job requirements J , List of available compute endpoints E , Resource histograms [23] for each endpoint H .
 - 2: **Output:** Sorted list of compute endpoints based on matching scores and resource availability.
 - 3: **Step 1:** *Initialize the Job requirements and endpoints*
 - 4: Define job requirements $J = \{\text{cpu_cores}, \text{memory}\}$.
 - 5: For each compute endpoint $e_i \in E$:
 - 6: Collect resource histograms from each endpoint: H_i for CPUs and memory.
 - 7: **Step 2:** *Filter out endpoints that cannot meet the basic resource requirements*
 - 8: **for** each endpoint $e_i \in E$ **do**
 - 9: **if** The endpoint is online (i.e., e_i 's status = "online") **then**
 - 10: Retrieve the CPU and memory histogram for e_i : $H_i = \{\text{cpu_histogram}, \text{memory_histogram}\}$.
 - 11: Check if the endpoint has sufficient resources for the job:
 - 12: **if** There exists a machine in e_i with enough free CPUs and memory **then**
 - 13: Mark e_i as a viable destination.
 - 14: **else**
 - 15: Skip e_i (it cannot meet the job requirements).
 - 16: **end if**
 - 17: **end if**
 - 18: **end for**
 - 19: **Step 3:** *Calculate the distance to input data location*
 - 20: **for** each viable endpoint e_i **do**
 - 21: Calculate the distance from e_i to the job's input data location: $\text{distance_to_data}(e_i)$.
 - 22: **end for**
 - 23: **Step 4:** *Calculate the matching score for each endpoint*
 - 24: **for** each viable endpoint e_i **do**
 - 25: Calculate the matching score $\text{score}(e_i)$ based on the following criteria:
 - 26: Queue matching factor: $\text{qm}(e_i) = \frac{1}{\text{median_queue_time}(e_i) \times \text{queue_size}(e_i)}$
 - 27: Compute matching factor: $\text{cm}(e_i) = \frac{1}{\text{median_run_time}(e_i) \times \text{running_jobs}(e_i)}$
 - 28: Total matching score: $\text{score}(e_i) = \text{qm}(e_i) + \text{cm}(e_i)$
 - 29: **end for**
 - 30: **Step 5:** *Sort endpoints by matching score and distance to data location*
 - 31: Sort the endpoints first by their matching scores in descending order:

$$\text{sorted_endpoints} = \text{sort}(E, \text{by score})$$
 - 32: If matching scores are tied, sort by distance to the input data location in ascending order.
 - 33: **Step 6:** *Allocate jobs to sorted endpoints*
 - 34: Allocate jobs to the sorted endpoints based on the order. Each job is allocated to the most suitable endpoint based on:
 - 35: Available CPUs and memory on the endpoint.
 - 36: The job's matching score with the endpoint.
 - 37: **Step 7:** *Return the allocated endpoints*
 - 38: Return the list of allocated endpoints ordered by matching score and data proximity.
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